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Study of Physical Properties of Soil and Soil Texture

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Abstract:

Physical properties of soil is very important. In the field of Agriculture sector India is a fast growing country. Agriculture sector playing key role on GDP of India. This sector fulfills not only food grains requirement of country but also provides raw materials for various industrial sectors. It is possible only due to deep study of physical environment and proper study of behavior of soil using physical and chemical properties with technological tools. A small attempt has been made by the author to study physical properties and soil texture. It has been also seen that soil rich of Clay content has more transition point moisture value (Wt) then that of sandy soils. Physical and Chemical properties of soil also shows

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significant variation in dielectric properties. One can use this properties to predict the fertility properties of soil. This study can be helpful to enhance the productivity of crops. Further it has been tabulated the textural analysis of different places.

Keywords: Soil texture, Transition property, Physical properties, soil, agriculture, tool.

1. Introduction:

Soil may be defined as a thin layer of earth's crust which serves as a natural medium for the growth of plants. It is the unconsolidated mineral matter that has been subjected to, and influenced by genetic and environmental factors parent material, climate, organisms and topography all acting over a period of time. Soil differs from the parent material in the morphological, physical, chemical and biological properties. Also, soils differ among themselves in some or all the properties, depending on the differences in the genetic and environmental factors. Thus some soils are red, some are black; some are deep and some are shallow; some are coarse-textured and some are fine textured. They serve in varying degree as a reservoir of nutrients and water for crops, provide mechanical anchorage and favourable tilth. The components of soils are mineral material, organic matter, water and air, the proportions of which vary and which together form a system for plant growth; hence the need to study the soils in perspective.

A developed soil will have a well-defined profile which is a vertical section of the soil through all its horizons and it extends up to the parent materials. The horizons (layers) in the soil profile which may vary in thickness may be distinguished from morphological characteristics which include colour, texture, structure, etc. Generally, the profile consists of three mineral horizons - A, B and C. Physical properties of the soil include water holding capacity, aeration, plasticity, texture, structure, density and colour, etc.

1.1 Major Soil Types of India:

Some dominant groups of Indian soil, classified according to soil taxonomy and chemical property are mentioned below:

- Red Soil: They are quite wide in their spread. The red colour is due to diffusion of iron in the profile.
- Lateritic Soil: Lateritic soil are composed of a mixture of hydrated oxides of aluminium and iron with small amounts of manganese oxide.
- Black Soil: Black soil contains a high proportion of Calcium and Magnesium Carbonates and have a high degree of fertility.
- Alluvial Soils: This is the largest and agriculturally most important group of soils.
- Desert Soils: Desert soils occur mostly in dry areas and important content is quartz.
- Forest and Hill Soils high in organic matter.

Fig. 1: Agro-Ecological Region Map of India

1.2 Soil Physical Properties:

1.2.1 Sand: Large particles which are coarse, and individual particles are easily visible (0.02 - 2 mm in diameter) most common mineral component is silica (SiO_2)

Fig. 2: Sand

1.2.2 Silt: Medium-sized particles which are 0.002-0.02 mm in diameter.

Fig. 3: Silt

1.2.3 Clay: Small particles which are less than 0.002 mm in diameter and are referred to as soil colloids.

Fig. 4: Clay

By definition, particles larger than sand are not soil.

Fig. 5: Sand, Silt, Clay

1.2.4 Liquid Phase:

- Soil water which occupies the pore spaces (between mineral particles) carries the plant nutrients to the roots.

Fig. 6: Liquid Phase

1.2.5 Soil Air:

- It occupies pore spaces similar to soil water. It fills these voids when soil water is absent.
- It carries respiratory products of roots and soil-organisms.
- It has a higher concentration of carbon dioxide than atmospheric air.

Fig. 7: Soil Air

1.2.6 Soil Texture:

- Refers to the relative proportion of sand, silt and clay present in a soil.
- Based on these proportions soils are classified into various textural classes.
- Clayey soils have a larger percent of clay. They are considered more fertile than sandy soils but are difficult to work.
- Sandy soils are easy to work but are less fertile. They have low water retention capacity.
- Loamy soils are in between sandy and clayey soils. They are best for arable cropping.

Fig. 8: Soil Texture

1.2.7 Soil Structure:

- Refers to the arrangement of the different particles into soil aggregates.
- Roots move between these aggregates.
- A compact soil will resist root movement.
- The organic matter content helps the soil aggregation process.

Fig. 9: Soil Structure

1.2.8 Soil Fertility:

It is the capacity of a soil to supply plant nutrients in adequate amounts to facilitate optimum growth and obtaining the yield potential of a crop.

Fig. 10: Soil Fertility

Many soil properties which determine the availability of plant nutrients and thus soil fertility are as follows:

1.2.9 Soil Colour:

Reddish to brownish colour shows well-drained conditions. Degree of yellowness and mottling show poor drainage. Gray to dark colour indicates the presence of organic material.

Fig. 11: Soil Colour

1.2.10 Soil Depth:

Refers to the depth to which plant roots can penetrate the soil and is the distance between the lowest and the upper most horizons of the soil.

Fig. 12: Soil Depth

1.2.11 Bulk Density:

It is the weight of the soil in the given volume. A compact soil has a higher value while an organic soil has a lower value. It also affects water holding capacity of the soil.

Fig. 13: Bulk Density

1.2.12 Field Capacity:

- Refers to the moisture content of a soil after the loss of gravitational water.
- At this point, water is held in soil micropores, which is available to plant roots, until the water content down to a lower value.
- This lower value is referred to as the permanent wilting point.
- The amount of water available between field capacity and permanent wilting point is referred to as available water.
- This value is important in determining irrigation intervals.

Fig. 14: Field Capacity

2. Theoretical Considerations:

With the help of formula, the particle density, field capacity, water holding capacity, moisture contents, and others useful parameters have been estimated. The data is cited from research paper of D.V.K. Narasingham which is same place.

Table 1: Textural analysis of different places

Sl. No.	Places	Textural Analysis		
		Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)
1	Kota	36	30	34
2	Akaltara	46	22	32
3	Pendra	50	22	28
4	Mungeli	42	32	26
5	Korba	54	24	22
6	Kharasia	48	20	32
7	Baramkela	44	26	30

3. Result & Discussion:

Fig. 15: Graphical representation of Soil Texture for different places

Table 2: Textural analysis with ISSS

Sl. No.	Places	Textural Analysis			Textural Class based upon ISSS (Fraction System)
		Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	
1	Kota	36	30	34	Silty clay loam
2	Akaltara	46	22	32	Clay loam
3	Pendra	50	22	28	Clay loam
4	Mungeli	42	32	26	Silty loam
5	Korba	54	24	22	Loam
6	Kharasia	48	20	32	Clay loam
7	Baramkela	44	26	30	Silty clay loam

4. Conclusions:

Physical properties have significant influence on the behaviour of soil for agricultural and engineering uses. Soil texture and structure determine the total porosity and the size distribution of pores which influence water, heat and air relationship in the soil. Soil texture is a static property but structure may be manipulated through management practices. It is essential to carry out the tillage operations at optimum soil moisture to avoid deterioration in soil structure. Management of physical, chemical, and biological factors can help in maintaining proper soil physical condition for plant growth. Soil aeration and soil temperature affect the quality of soils for plants and other organisms. Soil water has a major influence on both soil aeration and temperature. It competes with soil air and moderates soil temperature. Soil consistency, plasticity, compaction, strength, etc. help in determining the stability of soil against loading forces from traffic, tillage or building foundations. In present scenario at the current stress on soil as a natural resource for food security and safety, due emphasis is needed for maintaining soil physical fertility by adding organic materials, introduction of legumins in rotation, adoption of conservation tillage, etc.

References:

- Chaudhary H.C. (2015) : Dielectric Study of Soils With Varied Organic Matter At Microwave Frequency, IJCPS, Vol. 4, No. 3.
- https://www.google.com/search?q=soil+structure&rlz=1C1CHBF_enIN1004IN1004&sxsrf=APwXEdc50GM1-ybbNn_SFggccGmalvjK3g:1683627186665&source=lnms&tbn=isch&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwjrtSDgOj-AhWXTWwGHZNiAeMQ_AUoAXoECAEQAw&biw=1366&bih=625&dpr=1
- https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.kisaanhelpline.com%2Fresearch-article%2F165%2FSTUDY-AND-ANALYSIS-OF-SOIL-TEXTURE&psig=AOvVaw3uqiHx_RBek388NtwrXW7p&ust=1683714636727000&source=images&cd=vfe&ved=0CBEQjRxqFwoTCKjByfiD6P4CFQAAAAAdAAAAABAE
- Mohan Rajesh (2015) : Study And Analysis of Dielectric Behaviour of Fertilized Soil at Microwave Frequency, Euro, J. Adv. Engg. Tech. 2(2), 73-79.
- Nahire S.B. (2015) : Physico-Chemical and Dielectric Properties of Soil Samples At X-Band Microwave Frequency of Nasik Region, Bionant fronties, Vol. 8(3).
- Narayan Rajeshri (2011) : Remote Sensing Characteristics of Soil at X-Band Microwave Frequency Range 10.45 GHz, M.Phil. Dissertation.
- Navarkhele N.N. (2016) : Study of Two Indian Soils, Journal of Chemical And Pharmaceutical Research, 8(1): 153-160.
- Narasigham D.V. K., Shrivastava A.K., and Pandey Ashutosh : Comparative Study of Physico-Chemical Properties of Soil, Journal of Soils and Crops, Vol. 34 (2).
- Sahu Jaiprakash and Shrivastava A.K. (2023) : Soil Texture: Panacea for Agriculture, Eur. Chem. Bull. 12(1), 956-976.
- Chaudhary Reshu, Sahu Jaiprakash and Shrivastava A.K. (2023) : Impact Analysis of Variation in Soil Texture for Dielectric Behaviour, Eur. Chem. Bull. 12 (Special Issue 4), 7879-7886.